

Parsing migration paths from administrative language.

The case of Luxembourg files of migration administration

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Estelle Bunout

Administrative archives produce serial documents that lend themselves to data extraction, because of their regular format. The progress made, both in OCR/HTR and layout detection, opens up these large collections for the development of digitisation pipeline leading to computer readable data from analogue forms. However, these forms contain also unstructured text that needs specific processing to parse them.

We propose to discuss our experience in extracting information from administrative forms in which civil servants transcribed the ten past years of migration of declarants arriving to Luxembourg in the 20th century. These paragraphs contain precious information and follow a regular structure and vocabulary, referring to information located either in another part of the form or to other forms of the same archival fond.

In section 1, we introduce the source material and the research context. Following this, we will highlight the specific workflow utilized in this project. Special attention will be given to how we handle formulaic language within the administrative documents, a critical aspect of our methodology. In section 3, we will focus on the extraction process itself and the practical aspects of extracting information from the formulaic language of the administrative texts. We will discuss the techniques and tools employed to interpret and transform these archival documents into a format that is not only machine-readable but also conducive to further research and analysis.

1. Introduction: Source Presentation and Research Questions

From 1893 until 1972 (except for 1940-45), migrants reaching to Luxembourg had to register upon arrival at the communal administration. These declarations, recorded upon arrival, represent a snapshot of the migrants' situation as declared to the administration. While they lack post-arrival information, the accumulation of declarations over multiple returns or in the context of inter-city movement, can create a biographical narrative through cumulative data. The forms first appeared around 1911, replacing older tabular records. Their use dwindled with the establishment of a dedicated administration in the 1970s.

The source material is highly consistent, consisting of a standardized form with minor variations over a relatively short period. The workflow and tools employed allow for easy adaptation of the model to accommodate these slight changes. The focus here is on a specific section of the form, which changed in the 1960s, from a bloc of text to a pre-filled form, stating "from ... until...". Interestingly, sometimes employees would write in the form instead of using the pre-filled fields. We are interested in the text blocs for the 1910s until the 1960s. During this period, Luxembourg witnessed high industrial growth, accompanied by significant migration, making the archival series variable, fluctuating annually from over a thousand per city to a few hundred per city.

Physical copies are available in local municipalities, and personal files are centralized in the National Archives of Luxembourg (ANLux). The manual transcription of declarations from Dudelange has been tested for data extraction. The Differdange collection is digitized but not fully accessible. Data from other cities remains largely unexplored.

Example of an arrival declaration

Fremdenpolizei.
POLICE DES ÉTRANGERS.
Gefetz vom 30. Dezember 1902.
Loi du 30 décembre 1903.

Anmelde-Erklärung
Déclaration d'Arrivée N. 1352

für Dallanegra Gastano
faite par _____
welche sich niedergelassen hat zu Fonds de Gras, Colonie
(Ortsnachricht) (Quartier) (Bureau) (Adresse)
qui a pris résidence à _____
(Indiquer le nom de la rue ou l'établissement)
am 7. octobre 1922
le _____

1. Ort und Datum der Geburt (Orts- und Quartier n. 1. u. 2.) Lieu et date de naissance. (Arrondissement, département etc.) Nom et prénom Da père Nom et prénom Lieu de naissance	<u>Piacenza (Prov. Piacenza) 11.8.1880</u> <u>Angelo</u> <u>id.</u> <u>Barbieri Maria</u> <u>id.</u> <u>italienne</u> <u>mineur (Providence)</u> <u>célibataire</u>	
2. Der Vater Nom et prénom Da père Nom et prénom Lieu de naissance	<u>id.</u> <u>Barbieri Maria</u> <u>id.</u> <u>italienne</u> <u>mineur (Providence)</u> <u>célibataire</u>	
3. Der Mutter Nom et prénom Da la mère Nom et prénom Lieu de naissance	<u>id.</u> <u>Barbieri Maria</u> <u>id.</u> <u>italienne</u> <u>mineur (Providence)</u> <u>célibataire</u>	
4. Nationalität Nationalité du déclarant. Nom et prénom Lieu de naissance	<u>italienne</u> <u>mineur (Providence)</u> <u>célibataire</u>	
5. Stand oder Gewerbe Profession. Moyens d'existence, salaire, biens immobiliers etc.	<u>salaire</u>	
6. Ehestand, verheiratet oder ledig Marié, veuf ou célibataire.	<u>salaire</u>	
7. Ort und Datum der Eheschließung Lieu et date du mariage.	<u>Elberfeld, Kipdorfstr. 43, depuis le 23.7.1921</u> <u>Piacenza, Via Mazzini, 100, pendant 18 mois,</u> <u>Elberfeld, pendant 10 mois,</u> <u>Aspe (Hagen/Westf.), Ennepferstr. 43, pendant 4 ans</u> <u>Piacenza depuis sa naissance.</u>	
8. Der Ehegatte Nom et prénom Da conjoint Nom et prénom Lieu et date de naissance	<u>id.</u> <u>id.</u> <u>id.</u> <u>id.</u>	
9. *) Name, Geburtsort und Alter der Kinder. Nom, lieu de naissance et âge des enfants.	<u>id.</u> <u>id.</u> <u>id.</u> <u>id.</u>	
10. Angabe ob b. Indiquer si le déclarant est avec ou sans famille.	<u>id.</u> <u>id.</u> <u>id.</u> <u>id.</u>	
11. Erwerb- u. Vermögensverhältnisse (Einkommen, Grundbesitz etc.) Moyens d'existence, salaire, biens immobiliers etc.	<u>id.</u> <u>id.</u> <u>id.</u> <u>id.</u>	
12. Aufenthaltsort während der letzten 10 Jahre, unter möglichst genauer Bezeichnung der Orte und Aufenthaltsdauer in jeder Ort-Ortschaft. Résidence pendant les 10 dernières années, Indiquer la durée de séjour dans chaque localité, la rue et le No de la maison habitée et, le cas échéant, les noms du patron.	<u>id.</u> <u>id.</u> <u>id.</u> <u>id.</u>	
13. Datum der Date du	<u>id.</u> <u>id.</u> <u>id.</u> <u>id.</u>	
14. Ort und Datum der Impfung Lieu et date de la vaccination.	<u>id.</u> <u>id.</u> <u>id.</u> <u>id.</u>	

Stichtig bescheinigt Differdange den 11. octobre 1922
Certifié exact _____ le _____

Der Interessent. Dallanegra Gastano
L'Intéressé, _____
Der Polizei-Commissar.
Le Commissaire de Police, _____

*) Bemerkung. — Für großjährige Männer und für Familien sind besondere Anmeldeblätter nach demselben Formular auszugeben.
REMARQUE. — Établir d'après le même formulaire, une déclaration spéciale pour les majeurs et les domestiques.

Fields contained in the form:

- Name of the declarant
- Place of residence
- Date of arrival
- Father (name and place, date of birth)
- Mother (name and place, date of birth)
- Nationality
- Profession
- Marital status
- Date and place of marriage
- Spouse (name and place, date of birth)
- Children
- Presence of the family
- Income
- Residence over the past ten years
- Identification
- Vaccination status
- Date and time of declaration
- Civil servant receiving the declaration
- Signature of the declarant
- Picture

1: Source : Archives of Differdange, 4 E 8 86 - Police des étrangers - Déclarations d'arrivée 1351-1689 - 04/11/1922-30/12/1922, p.2, <https://archives.differdange.lu/ark:/24628/568429.584455/daoqrp/0/2>

Once processed, the data can be used to search for names, birthplaces, filter by dates, professions, etc. The quality and type of information necessary depend on the research questions posed. The main challenge lies in connecting data for long-term studies. The goal is to create a dataset that faithfully represents the archive with minimal data modelling. Automation poses its own set of challenges and limitations, including probabilistic approaches, differentiation between transforming scanned data into parsable data, and historical analysis.

We aim at creating datasets that rely on the transcription and an enrichment that does not transform the data model transposing the original structure of the administrative form. These datasets can then be used to create specific research corpora; be connected to each other; to other similar collections in other countries or even to contextual archives.¹

These sources have been used in various research contexts, such as migration history,² World War II history, and the Holocaust in Luxembourg.³ The creation of several datasets transposing administrative archival collections may enable a kind of data-driven history of administrative practices: understanding the central administration's concerns reflected in the administrative forms versus the information collected, reflected in the transcriptions, the administrative procedures experienced by individuals or groups, and comparison with neighbouring countries.

2.Context: a Pipeline to Transcribe, Extract and Connect Data from Arrival Declarations

One of the primary benefits of using forms is that if the digitization process is consistent, the information is generally located in the same area on each form. This uniformity facilitates easier data extraction and analysis. The current advancements in transcription and layout tools have significantly simplified the processing of administrative documents. However, a key challenge remains in extracting information from these documents, particularly given their structured format.

We defined a pipeline transforming the source material into machine readable documents with increasing granularity. First, the documents have to be transcribed into machine readable formats, and the peculiarity of the transcription of administrative forms should keep the information attached to each field, to make the work with the

¹ Hoekstra et Koolen, « Data scopes for digital history research »; Hoekstra, Koolen, et van Faassen, « Vested Authorities, Emergent Brokers and User Archivists »; Oprel, « Paper trails to private lives ».

² Venken et Sauer, « Arrival Declaration Forms. A New Gateway for Mapping Migration to Luxembourg ». See also: the research conducted by Arnaud Sauer, Daniel Richter and the projects « Colonial History of Luxembourg (COLUX) »; « Fleeting and Lasting Presence ».

³ Scuto et Gloden, « Introduction au Colloque ».

transcription possible at larger scale. We present this step quickly below. Next, some fields of the form contain larger bloc of texts that need some specific manipulation to transform the bloc into individual bits of information, as we will describe under section 3. Then the output of both steps can be enriched with geographical information and connected to other similar sources from other cities or other periods.

2: Pipeline for administrative archive collections.

2.1 Transcribing the administrative forms

In this project we use off the shelf tools, Transkribus, provided by READ-COOP SCE, but solutions might be developed specially for this task, as was done for the Hungarian national archive, or office solutions offered by commercial compagnies to deal with receipts or other types of form.

Below is a screenshot of the Transkribus lite, online platform, where we can see side by side the facsimile of the form and its transcription. The coloured blocs highlight the layout that has been detected on the form. The transcription follows the fields detected, resulting in labels attached to each transcribed line. Each scanned page results in a labelled transcription and all contents for each label can be collected as such. In other words, the transcribed text with labels can be compiled into sheets, where one line represents the output for one page and the columns represent each label, or original field of the archive. This makes it very easy to process later on.

3: Screenshot of the Transkribus Lite platform displaying the facsimile and transcription of an Arrival Declaration.

After the transcription process is complete and we have individual fields in separate cells, we can delve deeper to extract more granular data from these fields. While some fields, such as dates and birthplaces of the declarant, spouse, and parents, are relatively straightforward, it is the complex fields that often prove to be the most challenging, such as a field for previous residences. In this field, we need further processing to extract pairs of time and places, as we will see in section 3. These pairs are needed to plot points on a map or a chronology and enable connection to other collections or geographical information for the places mentioned. As we will see, while the time-place pairs extracted can have a degree of imprecision, what is critical is accurately pairing relevant date and time information, as this forms the backbone of effectively mapping historical movements and residences.

2.2 Connecting the fields

A critical part of the connection process involves matching place mentions from various fields (birth places of the declarant, the mother, father, spouse, etc.) with resources like GeoNames or historical gazetteers, which accommodate spelling variations and minor errors, thus allowing a margin for mistakes or abbreviations. A significant

challenge, however, lies in the disambiguation of homonyms, where places with the same name need to be correctly identified. For this step, we use another off the shelf solution: the web-based data management, network analysis & visualisation environment, NodeGoat.⁴ This platform enables us to collect, store and connect datapoints.

The connection process relies on the use fuzzy matching techniques to manage place mentions, available in NodeGoat, which is essential due to the variability in spellings resulting from OCR errors, spelling mistakes by civil servants, or historical changes in place names, as seen with examples like Przeworsk, a Polish city for which we collected 14 different spelling variations. Differentiating between cities sharing the same name is a significant challenge, and the choices made in such cases can be complex. If a decision is made for one homonym, it might be incorrectly applied to another. Despite these challenges, two main sources of errors—homonyms and spelling variations—can be manually corrected post-identification, as we keep track of the original transcribed spelling.

This principle of harmonization and normalization extends beyond place mentions to other data fields like professions and nationalities. These processes are key to facilitating the creation of links between documents and individuals. However, as with place mentions, it's important to approach these processes with a focus on maintaining data integrity and transparency. This ensures that the data remains accurate and useful for various applications and research needs.

As the lists of normalised terms are relatively short and because we are keeping the original mentions attached to the individuals and the source materials, they can be easily updated, to increase or decrease the granularity depending on the research question. This applies particularly to the professions, where in the mentions, the company is often mentioned but disappears in the normalised list. The professions changed also in content and social standing over time, which can require a dedicated modelisation, which remains possible.

In the spirit of transparency inspired by the Data Scope and acknowledging the impossibility of predicting all future uses of the dataset, maintaining different versions

⁴ Bree, P. van, Kessels, G., (2013). nodegoat: a web-based data management, network analysis & visualisation environment, <http://nodegoat.net> from LAB1100, <http://lab1100.com>

of the dataset is essential. There are several versions of the dataset: including before the connection process, which includes a list of already detected cities, and a post-connection version. While individual cases can still be corrected, since the connection between each person and the source is retained, along with the original and normalized city names, the output should be used cautiously.

3. Extracting time and place data from the migration narration in the Arrival Declarations

After looking at the first and last steps of the pipeline, we'll dive now in the middle step: the extraction of data from text blocs, relying on the regularity of the administrative vocabulary, prefiguring the form of the 1960s. As the source material is available in digital (e.g. manual transcription for the city of Dudelange) and analogue form (e.g. scanned by the city of Differdange), for the extraction we used the manually transcribed material because of its higher quality but will apply the steps to the scanned materials. All extraction presented here has been conducted on the manually transcribed material, the next step will be applying it to the automatically transcribed material, which may be impacted by the OCR mistakes, mitigated by the fuzzy matching.

3.1 From pairs to extraction rules

The description of the past residences follows regular patterns, though there are a few of them. We'll start by describing some simple cases, that we used to set some rules for the extraction of date and place mentions. Typically, the statements start with "comes from...", the next segment of information is introduced by "before that". Another popular introduction is "since birth", as shown in the examples below.

Original text	Targeted output (pairs of time and space data)		
Kommt von Bissen wo er seit dem 23.08.1909 war vorher im Heiderscheidergrund.	Bissen, 23-08-1909	Heiderscheidgrund, 22-08-1909	
Seit Geburt (26.07.1896) zu Düdelingen.	Düdelingen, 26-07-1896		
Vom 01.01.1909 bis Juli 1909 zu Kamphausen vorher 6 Monate zu Marel-Westphalen vorher 1 Jahr zu Hannover.	Kamphausen, 1-07-1909	Marel-Westphalen, 1-06-1908	Hannover, 1-06-1907

Sometimes, both time and place are implied rather than explicitly mentioned, requiring a nuanced approach to infer these details from the context. In other instances, the time might be implicit, with the place clearly stated, which calls for a method that focuses on identifying the explicit place while deducing the associated time. The most straightforward scenario is when both time and place are explicitly mentioned, simplifying the extraction process.

In cases where there is a simple pattern, such as the mention of a place of origin without a corresponding mention of time, the extraction and detection process become more complex, meaning a few other steps are needed. Merely identifying the place of origin is not sufficient; it becomes essential to detect the implicit date associated with it. As in the example below, only the place is mentioned. A rule is needed to add the relevant information and make the data useable.

4: Example of a simple statement and the steps to enrich with other information contained in the dataset.

The extraction focuses on time and place, leaving aside other information, such as the mention of the residence with the family or the military service. Below we can see that three distinct formulations lead to the same type of result.

5: Examples of variable ways to express the same pair of information.

6: Example of period mentions and the suggested rules.

After identifying the patterns in the data, these can be translated into a coherent set of rules designed to streamline the extraction process. This includes rules for detecting explicit mentions within the data, which is a straightforward task. Another important aspect is the translation of references, which serves as a pre-extraction step. This involves converting terms like birth ("Geburt") to their corresponding information from a designated cell, from the transcribed dataset.

Additionally, the calculation of periods, especially those expressed in months, is handled in the pre-extraction phase. This is vital for accurately interpreting the duration mentioned in the data. A notable challenge arises with periods where dates are

explicitly mentioned. In such cases, two dates are often extracted, potentially complicating the process of pairing the data correctly.

Based on these observations, Mehrdad Almasi developed a script that we will describe below. A few selections and simplifications were decided: for instance, the choice to focus solely on cities (not streets when mentioned). The extraction is therefore not one to one.

The first step of the algorithmic processing relies in these rule-based replacement (the word “birth” with the actual birth date, calculations for periods expressed in days, months, years). The next step consists in applying Named Entity Recognition for (SpaCy and FLAIR) to identify the places and dates mentioned in the original text, enriched with the replacements. The output consists in a list of places and dates that then would need to be paired back together.

3.2 Unresolved challenge: from extracted data to pairs.

A good indicator of the number of pairs to identify seems to be the number of places mentioned, as the expression of periods may create some confusion. As the number of pairs increases, particularly when dealing with more implicit information, the process becomes progressively complex. There seems to be no straightforward way to formulate rules to recreate the time and space pairs. For instance, the assumption that two detected items, considering that some implicit references were mostly replaced by explicit mentions, would lead to a pair, is not verified. We took as an example, the extracted items for the year 1910 and the city of Dudelange and matched each line to the actual numbers of pairs the text bloc contained.

Evaluation of the extracted items – example of the year 1910

# of detected items	# of pairs					Total
	1	2	3	4	5	
1	448	1			1	450
2	79	40				119
3	3	266	6			275
4		376	43			419
5		49	201	4		254
6		2	137	25		164
7			28	37	3	68
8			3	33	1	37
9				4	3	7
10				2	1	3
11					1	1
12					1	1
Total	530	734	418	105	11	1798

Out of 1798 declaration texts, 530 contain one pair of time and space information and 734 two pairs, while 418 contain three pairs. In other words, the vast majority of declared migration paths contain only one previous stay, or two and a little less three, which seems to offer a limited range of complexity. However, there seem to be no simple way to define rules for the pairing of these items. We have started to experiment with ChatGpt from OpenAI⁵ to interpret the text blocs to extract and pair the time and place information. The first results seem promising but not solid enough. We need to find a more controlled way to make use the large language models to pair back the detected items.

⁵ See the Dudelage Data Extractor: <https://chat.openai.com/g/g-hEGa5dF2s-dudelage-data-extractor> created by Lars Wienecke.

4. Outlook: Towards Parsable Administrative Migration Archives

As we have seen, each step of the pipeline leads to a version of a dataset that reflects an archival collection with richer contents that can be reused or connected in various research contexts.

The next critical question is how to scale up these processes effectively. Scaling up involves not only increasing the volume of data processed but also ensuring the robustness and adaptability of our methods to handle diverse and larger datasets. This expansion promises significant advancements in administrative, data-driven historical research.

The potential for history in the context of data-driven administrative records is vast. By employing techniques like Linked Open Data (LOD) and Resource Description Framework (RDF), we can create more interconnected and accessible historical databases, transposing the data scope principle to our datasets.⁶ These methods

⁶ de Boer et al., « A Linked Data Model for Data Scopes ».

allow for the creation of comprehensive schemas based on source transcription. The approach should involve a schema that is closely aligned with the source materials and their transcriptions. This method would ensure that the data retains its original context and meaning, thereby providing a richer and more accurate source for research in digital history.

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